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MAKEEVA I. I.

Scientific Library, Oles Honchar Dnipro National University (Dnipro, Ukraine),

e-mail: makevirina@i.ua

PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF A LIBRARIAN OF A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

Objective. Development and implementation of the concept of professional competencies of librarians. **Methods.** In the course of the research, a complex of methods of theoretical analysis (terminological analysis; literature analysis) and synthesis was used; methods of comparison, generalization, systematization of an array of publications. **Results.** The study of the research on the development and implementation of the professional competence of librarians made it possible to identify the necessary requirements for university library specialists. The resulting practice revealed the potential of librarians during telecommuting. **Conclusions.** In modern scientific theory, the concept of human competence has a broad interpretation and a complex structural structure. In general, it is about the ability of a person to perform certain activities, perform tasks or work; the availability of an appropriate set of knowledge, skills and attitudes that enable them to act effectively in a professional field or activity. Professional competencies of librarians are necessary for the implementation of professional activities, opportunities for self-improvement throughout life.

Keywords: professional competencies; university library specialist; university library

Introduction

Informatization has changed all spheres of human activity, including the content of the work of libraries of higher educational institutions.

The activity of a university librarian is diverse, it manifests itself in the effective use of existing experience, in the ability to see options for solving the same problem and non-standard approaches to the development of new forms, means, techniques and methods of transferring information.

Methods

In the course of the research, a complex of methods of theoretical analysis (terminological analysis; literature analysis) and synthesis was used; methods of comparison, generalization, systematization of an array of publications.

Results and Discussion

The relevance of the research is determined by the contradictions arising in the process of retraining and advanced training of librarians:

- between the constantly increasing requirements for the education system, including additional vocational education, the growing level and pace of development of the information society and its ability to comply with these processes;
- between the potentialities of information resources, means for their use;
- between the need for active and constant work of librarians and the existing opportunities for the manifestation of creative activity, independence and individuality when using standard approaches and technologies.

In world educational practice, the concept of competence acts as a central, a kind of "key" concept - for competence, firstly, combines the intellectual and skills components of education; secondly, the concept of competence contains the ideology of integrating the content of education, which is formed from the result; thirdly, key competence has an integrative nature, for it incorporates a number of homogeneous or closely related skills and knowledge related to broad spheres of culture and activity.

The concept of competence/competency is not a modern invention. It appeared in the famous Webster's New World Dictionary of the English (*New Webster's Dictionary and Thesaurus*, 2003) language at the end of the 16th century, but became widespread in the 90s of the last century. The number of definitions of this concept is very large, but its limits are quite finite, if you find common elements in all definitions or classify them according to two fundamental themes that give rise to differences in the definition of competencies.

In the dictionary of foreign words, competence is defined as "possession of knowledge that allows one to judge something, express a weighty authoritative opinion" or "possession of competencies, awareness, informedness, authority" (*Slovnyk Inshomovnykh Sliv*, 2000). "Competence" is understood as "the terms of reference of any organization, institution or person; the range of issues in which this person has the authority, knowledge, experience". The concept "competent" is interpreted as "experienced, knowledgeable in a certain area, who has the right, on the basis of his knowledge or authority, to do or decide something, judge something" (*Slovnyk Inshomovnykh Sliv*, 2000).

A special contribution to the understanding of these phenomena was made by D. C. McClelland, R. Boyatzis, J. Raven, L. Spencer and S. Spencer, S. Whiddett and S. Hollyforde, D. Brittel and others.

In 1973, David C. McClelland's article "Testing for Competence Rather Than Intelligence" was published, which is considered to be the beginning of the study of competencies. According to the author, the competency-based approach should analyze the success of the employee in the process of his/her work (McClelland, 1973).

But special attention to the problem of competencies was caused by the works of R. Boyatzis, especially his monograph "Competent Manager. Model of Effective Work". It was a generalization of the results of characteristics studies directly related to the specialists work effectiveness, regardless of the characteristics of the activities of their organizations. From the point of view of R. Boyatzis, in addition to competencies, the functional requirements of the work itself, as well as the conditions of the organizational environment, should be considered the components of the efficiency of work performance (Boyatzis, 2008).

Outstanding English psychologist John Raven in his work "Competence in modern society: blew, development and implementation" defines competence as the presence of a person's characteristics and abilities that allow him to achieve personally significant goals, regardless of their nature and social environment in which these people live and work (Raven, 1984).

The author notes that the phenomenon of competence includes intellectual, emotional and volitional components that provide effective motivation and a person's ability to implement it.

Subsequently, there were many publications of both theoretical and applied nature, the purpose of which was to define these concepts and their essential characteristics. Thus, L. Spencer and S. Spencer (2005) understand under the competence "the basic quality of an individual, which has a causal relationship to effective and/or best based on performance criteria in work or other situations." They identified the following types of basic competencies: motives, psychophysiological characteristics, self-concept, knowledge, skill.

According to Steve Whiddett, Sarah Hollyforde most of the definitions are different modifications of two themes, the differences of which are only in the sources of origin. In one case, competence is understood as "the ability ... to carry out their work in accordance with the standards adopted in the organization". In the other, competence is defined as the main characteristic of a personality that allows its owner to achieve high results in activity. The same authors explain the difference between the concepts of "competence" and "competency" (Whiddett & Hollyford, 2008).

According to M. N. Bakulina (2010), it is the use of acquired knowledge in activities that determines the competence of a person: "a person is either competent, or not in relation to a certain level of digestion".

In the scientific heritage of L. I. Moroz (2007) "competence is defined as structured sets of knowledge, abilities, skills and relationships of a person, which are formed in the learning process and allow a person to determine, identify and solve problems characteristic of a certain direction of productive activity".

So, professional competence is defined as an integrated characteristic of a specialist's personality, which is understood as the presence of a complex of relations, values, knowledge, skills and abilities necessary for the successful implementation of professional activity, manifested in the ability to perceive individual professional and social needs; in ensuring social and professional self-realization in the conditions of market relations in the possibility of professional self-improvement throughout life (Moroz, 2007).

But the common basis that characterizes the point of view of various authors is that a person's knowledge is a potential, scientific and practical baggage that he/she has, but only additional factors can put them into action. This means that competence is not only the availability of knowledge and experience, but also the ability to use them in the course of exercising their powers.

The Council of Europe has identified five key professional competencies to which it attaches particular importance:

1. Political and social competences, which include the ability of an individual to take responsibility, participate in joint decision-making, regulate conflicts, situations of cognitive dissonance, participate in the functioning and improvement of democratic social institutions.

2. Multicultural competences related to life in a cross society, such as understanding ethnic and national differences, respect for each other, the ability to respect people of other cultures, languages and religions.

3. Communicative competences, which provide for effective mastery of oral and written speech, which is quite important both in professional activity and in public life.

4. Information competencies associated with the emergence of information space in the society. It is assumed that a specialist will master new information technologies, understand the subject's attitude to information and advertising, disseminating in the media (European Commission (DG EAC), 2004).

Let us consider in more detail the above competencies.

Functional competence is the ability to extract new knowledge from various sources, from the study of one's own activities in the labor sphere, namely, these are the skills of:

- independent work with various sources of information;
- analysis of the situations arising in the process of labor activity;
- formulation of professional tasks, acquisition of new knowledge necessary for their productive solution;

- study, generalization and implementation of the best practices.

Personal competence is the readiness for continuous development, actualization and realization of one's personal and professional potential. This competence is manifested in the ability to think analytically and implement an integrated approach to the performance of one's official duties.

Special attention should be paid to the culture of professional communicative behavior – an indispensable attribute of the effective image of the staff of a modern library, which manifests itself in interaction with other subjects of library activity – users, colleagues, business partners.

Communicative competence defines complex processes of interaction in the library environment, consisting in the information exchange, perception and understanding of communication by partners.

Communicative competence, which is based on a humane attitude towards a person, realizes the benevolent, tactful, attentive behavior of a librarian. This is extremely important in view of the humanitarian mission of libraries.

The problem of successful library communication is relevant for researchers of the library image and librarians. For real success, creating an integral, positive image, a communicative culture is needed, which not only affects the attractiveness of the image, but also allows you to achieve professional goals, solve professional problems.

Communicative competence is the ability and real readiness for communication, goals, spheres and communication situations, readiness for verbal interaction and mutual understanding, both interpersonal and intercultural.

Communication skills:

- to establish optimal relationships with colleagues;
- find contact, common language and the right tone with different users and in different circumstances;
- express your thoughts clearly, logically, convincingly, figuratively and in an accessible way;
- exercise emotional restraint in all situations.

Traditional forms of library communication should be further developed and improved taking into account the requirements of modern society, and this is, first of all, the creation of a positive moral and psychological climate for library staff and users.

The fundamental importance in the implementation of the idea of a single information space is played by the English-speaking competence of librarians, with the help of which it becomes possible to achieve mutual understanding and interaction between representatives of various linguistic and cultural communities.

English-speaking competence is a personal and professional characteristic of a librarian, demonstrating the level of compliance with the requirements of professional library activity in the information society, the ability and willingness to use English to solve problems of library activity.

The content of this integrated competence includes:

- readiness for multitasking with global information resources;
- readiness to organize information activities and library and information services for readers in the global information space;
- readiness to present domestic information resources in the global information space.

The lack of formation of this competence of the human resource of librarianship is a barrier in the creation of a single information space both at the national and supranational levels; difficulties arise in intercultural communication and in solving the problems posed by modern society to the libraries of the present and the future.

Digital competence is the readiness, ability and responsibility to effectively select and apply information technologies to solve production problems.

Digital competence is considered as a combination of three components: informational (the ability to work effectively with information in all its representations); computer (skills and abilities of working with modern computer devices and software); application components (the ability to use modern information and computer technology devices in working with information to solve various production problems).

The need to ensure the readiness of society for such processes as mastering key combinations of knowledge, abilities, skills, ways of thinking, attitudes, other personal qualities in the field of information-communication and digital technologies (digital competence) was presented in the order of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine "On Approval of the Concept development of digital competencies and approval of an action plan for its implementation" dated March 3, 2021. (Pro skhvalennia Kontseptsii, 2021).

In the multifunctional activity of a librarian, more than in any other profession, society appreciates not only the level of education, the amount of special knowledge, skills, and abilities of specialists, but also moral qualities, which are understood as stable manifestations of moral consciousness in decision-making, behavior and self-presentation. And social competence is proof of that.

Social competence is the willingness to take responsibility, work in a team, develop a joint solution and participate in its implementation.

Ethical and culturally general competences are a priority among the key competencies of the librarian. They are an indicator and at the same time the result of the professional and personal readiness of the librarian to work, because the performance of any professional task has moral content.

Ethical competence represents and regulates the main actions that are consolidated in the skills, traditions, principles of life and professional activity, mental states, actions, deeds and qualities of a university librarian. General cultural competence is understood as the formation of the spiritual and moral qualities of a person, for whom humanism, responsiveness, honesty, kindness, and justice are most valuable.

The moral position of the librarian, based on universal human ideals and values, principles and norms of library ethics and deontology, is a set of moral relations, value orientations in social, professional and personal space.

The system of value orientations reflects a conscious choice of lifestyle and activity, attitude to life realities, determines the need-motivational sphere, having a significant influence on the success of professional activity. It is the value orientations, ideas about good and evil, about the ideal, the moral goal that constitute the axiological aspect of the librarian's moral position.

The pandemic revealed existing problems in the work of libraries:

✓ Technical unpreparedness of libraries of higher educational institutions to quick transition to online library services in accordance with all criteria of quality and efficiency.

✓ Lack of readiness of librarians to respond quickly for changes; insufficiency (or lack) of the competencies necessary to work in a digital educational environment; psychological unpreparedness (unwillingness) to learn.

Actual tasks:

- ✓ For libraries - system integration for automation of the library with the information infrastructure of the university.
- ✓ Implementation of virtual library services (electronic documents delivery, bibliographic information, exhibitions, communication means, assistance in the formation of lists of literature and the selection of sources for the development of educational programs, information support for the distance education system).

Conclusions

In the future, the role of the library staff will change, new competencies will be in demand. This is reflected in the tasks, functions and job titles: librarian, information disseminator, project manager, event organizer, information facilitator, etc.

As a consequence, the development of competencies will be an important element in the development of libraries. Whether current or future competencies are acquired through formal training or experience: the key is that libraries continue to train their staff to be prepared to meet the needs of users regardless of the type of institution.

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МАКЕЕВА І. І.

Наукова бібліотека, Дніпровський національний університет імені Олеся Гончара
(Дніпро, Україна), e-mail: makevirina@i.ua

ПРОФЕСІЙНІ КОМПЕТЕНЦІЇ СПЕЦІАЛІСТА БІБЛІОТЕКИ ВИЩОГО НАВЧАЛЬНОГО ЗАКЛАДУ

Мета. Розробка і реалізація концепції професійних компетенцій бібліотечних працівників.
Методика. У процесі проведення дослідження використовувався комплекс методів теоретичного аналізу (термінологічний аналіз; аналіз літератури) та синтезу; методи порівняння, узагальнення, систематизації масиву публікацій. **Результати.** Вивчення досліджень про розробку і реалізацію професійних компетенцій бібліотечних фахівців дозволило виявити необхідні вимоги до бібліотекарів університетських бібліотек. Ця практика сприяла розкриттю потенціалу бібліотекарів під час роботи в дистанційному режимі. **Висновки.** У сучасній науковій теорії поняття компетентності людини має широке трактування і складну структурну будову. Загалом йдеться про здатність людини кваліфіковано здійснювати певну діяльність, виконувати завдання чи роботу; наявність відповідних компетенцій щодо знань, навичок і відносин, що дозволяють ефективно діяти у професійній галузі або працювати у різних видах діяльності. Професійні компетенції бібліотекарів потрібні для реалізації ефективної діяльності, можливості самовдосконалення протягом усього життя.

Ключові слова: професійні компетенції; спеціаліст бібліотеки ЗВО; бібліотека закладу вищої освіти

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